

Figure S20. Raw correlation matrix of morphological traits.

Figure S21. Phylogenetically corrected matrix of morphological traits.

Figure S22. Macroevolutionary cohort analysis of speciation rates and Temporal dynamics of extinction and diversification rates for distinct focal clades.

Figure S23. Comparison of ancestral range reconstruction models.

Figure S24. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X1~X14 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S25. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X15~X28 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S26. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X29~X42 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S27. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X43~X56 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S28. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X57~X70 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S29. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X71~X84 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S30. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X85~X98 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S31. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X99~X112 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S32. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X113~X126 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S33. Diversification, speciation and extinction rates of traits X127~X142 under the best-fit model inferred by HiSSE and MuSSE.

Figure S34. Gryllidea region clade and the extent of regional diversity hotspots.

Figure S35. Comparison of speciation, extinction, and dispersal rates between hotspots and other non-hotspot regions

Figure S36. Speciation, extinction, and diversification rates per region between hotspots and other non-hotspot regions.